

D5.3 Communication and Dissemination report

31/10/2016

3D-games for TUNing and lEarning about hearing aids

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Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	4
List of Figures	4
Abbreviations and Acronyms	5
Executive Summary	6
Section 1. Introduction and background	7
Section 2. Overall strategy and progress	8
2.1 Overall progress up to M18	8
Section 3. Dissemination channels.....	10
3.1 Website: www.3d-tune-in.eu.....	10
3.1.1 Updates and modifications	11
3.1.2 Website modifications and updates from M4 (Aug, 2014) to M18 (Oct, 2016):.....	12
3.1.3 News section and blog.....	12
3.1.4 Upcoming updates.....	12
3.1.5 Results and Website Statistics.....	13
3.1.6 Ethics.....	15
3.2 Project materials	15
3.2.1 Videos.....	15
3.2.2 Branding.....	17
3.2.3 Posters, Banner and Roll-ups	17
3.3 Newsletter.....	21
3.3.1 Introductory Newsletter:.....	21
3.3.2 #1 Newsletter:.....	21
3.3.3 #2 Newsletter	21
3.3.4 #3 Newsletter	21
3.4 Section 4.4: Press releases and non-peer reviewed articles.....	21
3.5 Section 4.5: Academic Dissemination.....	22
3.6 Joint activities with other EU projects.....	26
3.7 Public presentations at fairs and events.....	26
3.8 Section 4.7: Social media activity.....	27
3.8.1 Strategy.....	27
3.8.2 Performance and statistics.....	29
Section 4. Dissemination activities.....	33
Section 5. Conclusions	46

List of Tables

Table 1: KPIs: results and estimates	8
Table 2: Relation of undertaken work with Task and Deliverables	9
Table 3: Summary of undertaken activities	9
Table 4: Sessions (M4-M18)	13
Table 5: Acquisition channels.....	14
Table 6: Demographic information	15
Table 7: Project Materials and link to public repositories.	18
Table 8: Press releases and non-peer reviewed articles.....	21
Table 9: Scientific dissemination activities	22
Table 10: Scientific dissemination - publications	24
Table 11: Workshop, fairs and trade events	26
Table 12: Overall strategy and minimum required interaction	28
Table 13: All-time top posts	29
Table 14: Twitter performance	30
Table 15: LinkedIn group - Geographical coverage.....	31
Table 16: Key Performance Indicators M1-M18 vs Estimates	46

List of Figures

Figure 1: Website homepage	10
Figure 2: Sessions (M1-M18).....	13
Figure 3: Introductory video to the 3DTI project: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dtzhiA5Xnvs 16	16
Figure 4: How can hearing loss impair speech and music listening? How can hearing aids improve this situation?- http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/audiodemos-hearing-aid-loss (hosted on YouTube)	16
Figure 5: Animation (Spanish, English and Italian) - http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/animation (also hosted on YouTube)	16
Figure 6: 3D Tune-In logos	17
Figure 7: Leaflet.....	18
Figure 8: Large Roll-up	19
Figure 9: Large Banner	19
Figure 10 - Press kits (Academia, left; General society, right)	20
Figure 11: Dartanan application (XTEAM) materials	20
Figure 12: Tweets and Profile visits.....	31
Figure 13: Overall impact estimated	46

Abbreviations and Acronyms

3DTI	3D Tune-In
BAHA	Bone Anchored Hearing Aid
BTE	Behind The Ear
CIC	Completely In Canal
DMU	De Montfort University
D&C Team	Dissemination and Communication Team
EU	European Union
GN	GN Hearing
ICL	Imperial College London
NLK	Nerlaska, S.L.
Reactify	Reactify Music
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
UMA	University of Malaga
UNott	The University of Nottingham
VIA	Vianet
WP	Work Package
XTeam	XTeam Software Solution

Executive Summary

This is the public deliverable D5.3 of the H2020 project 3D Tune-In (3DTI - 644051). This work was carried out as part of WP5 Communication and Dissemination. This document presents the communication and dissemination results of 3D Tune-In up to month 18.

Following a brief introduction to the overall communication strategy in Section 2, dissemination channels are defined in Section 3, together with a detailed analysis of the results. Section 4 presents the dissemination activities of the partners and Section 5 concludes the deliverable.

Section 1. Introduction and background

This is the public deliverable D5.3 of the H2020 project 3D Tune-In (3DTI - 644051). This work was carried out as part of WP5 Communication and Dissemination. The strategy for the communication and dissemination channels and target audiences for the 3D Tune-In outcomes was defined in deliverable D5.1 Communication and Dissemination strategy. The overall objectives followed by the Dissemination and Communication strategy are to:

- Define and implement an integrated **strategy** for dissemination and exploitation.
It will capture the project outputs and detail how to communicate and exploit them within target audiences in the scientific, technology and industrial communities.
- Promote results and **benefits** of the project to target audiences.
The key audiences will be defined as the project develops, but initial groups will be found within the games industry and hearing communities.
- Provide regular **information** about the project and its results to target audiences via the website, social media, relevant publications, conferences, fairs and exhibitions.
- Collaborate with international research and professional **networks**, and ongoing EU and national projects.

This document is structured as follows. Section 2 reiterates the overall strategy including an action plan for the different phases of the project and a summary of the overall progress up to month 18. Section 3 defines changes to the dissemination channels together with a detailed analysis of the results. Section 4 presents the dissemination activities of the partners to date and Section 5 concludes the deliverable.

Section 2. Overall strategy and progress

The phases of the overall communication and dissemination strategy (as defined in D5.1) were as follows.

Phase 1 - Initial outreach: This was the initial phase of the project (M1-M12). The consortium produced the first deliverables and presented the 3DTI Project to the various target groups. A good number of dissemination materials were created and distributed across several communication channels. These materials are mostly focus upon the overall orientation of the project.

Phase 2 – Consolidation: The Phase 2 (M12-M24) is focused on an effective content marketing strategy and the production of new videos, demo videos, posters, articles, etc. but ensuring the IPR protection of the Toolkit and Applications development. The content generation and duration are becoming increasingly important for all partners .

Phase 3 – 3DTI Applications presented to the public: The Phase 3 (M24-M30) will require additional efforts and a double marketing strategy: all partners would invest more individual efforts and the whole consortium must prepare and design new materials and guidelines for a joint exploitation and an effective communication of these results and outputs.

Phase 4 - Final results (everything released and evaluation): In this phase (M30-M34), the consortium will present its final reflections and recommendations, based upon the validation stage conducted during the project.

Besides these planned activities, partners might have the opportunity to communicate project results and progress by other dissemination activities. In these cases, partners must communicate¹ to NLK and the Coordinator all envisaged dissemination activities .

2.1 Overall progress up to M18

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) measure the performance in terms of Communication and Dissemination for evaluating the outcomes of the 3D Tune-In project. **Error! Reference source not found.** below shows the most important KPIs to be assessed, comparing activities up to M18 with the total expected by M36.

Table 1: KPIs: results and estimates

	Estimates (during 36 months)	Results (M1-M18)
Journal Articles	2	1
Conference publications	3	5
Scientific Workshops	3	3
EU-projects networked	3	5
MSc Thesis	3	0
PhD Dissertation	1	1 in progress

¹ The procedures for accepting and submitting Dissemination and Communication activities are detailed in D5.1.

The following **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.** show the overall progress in terms of deliverables and tasks and dissemination and communication activities undertaken by the partners.

Table 2: Relation of undertaken work with Task and Deliverables

Deliverable and Task number	Title	Deadline	Short description of work
D5.1 / T5.1.	Definition of the communication and dissemination strategy	May 2016	Delivered (M4) but some minor updates under discussion (pp.11-12)
D5.2 / T5.2.	Project dissemination: website, posters, brochures, videos...	May 2016	Delivered.
D5.3 / T5.3.	Dissemination activities: articles, conferences, events	M18 (October 2016)	Continuous assessment and data collection on impact indicators, communication and dissemination measurements and stats and activity reporting

Table 3: Summary of undertaken activities

	M1-M18
Articles	1
Conferences and seminars	9
Diss/Com materials ²	13
Non-peer reviewed articles	6
Press release	4
Workshop and fairs	17
Newsletters	4

² Banner, leaflet, roll up, Dartanan release (roll up, cover and banner), Italian-translated banner, Italian-translated leaflet, 5 videos and 2 press-kits are being considered as Dissemination Materials

Section 3. Dissemination channels

As planned in D5.1, a set of public materials have been produced for the partners to be able to disseminate the project results without the need of specific approval from the consortium. This material was approved and distributed among the partners. It included:

3.1 Website: www.3d-tune-in.eu

Figure 1: Website homepage

The website has been set up and has been online since July 2015. A Dissemination and Communication Team (D&C Team) has been formed by ICL, NLK and VIA. Its main role is to agree and establish the main Quality Assurance procedures and to coordinate the online dissemination activity. As part of the website management, the D&C Team has met often during these 18 months. The procedure for the coordination of the website content has been consolidated, with a monthly meeting where those topics in the Agenda, communication actions and campaigns related to the website are discussed.

The main procedures agreed for website revisions are the following:

NLK will check the website **weekly. The website check looks for bugs, issues and malfunctions on the website, such as missing images, format errors and response time.** If Energy House Digital (web designers) support is required, NLK will communicate the issue directly to ICL.

The website will be updated and new contents will be added at least once per month. Specifically, one new activity is expected to be published each month, while it also includes videos, new sub-pages, etc. **Language checks** have been agreed for ensuring the highest quality standards; NLK will carefully check and review each news item to be published. Then, it will be sent to either ICL, VIA or UNOTT for a final language review before its publication. Procedure; to send it out for internal review at least seven days in advance to the release deadline.

Also, an anticipatory contingency plan has been put in place. NLK will ask partners for brief articles/topics to feed future news section. ICL is willing to provide, when requested by NLK, updates about new technical items which could be considered good news topics. One news/article will always be kept non-published, for ensuring a regular flow of news on the website in case novel news items are not available in that specific period.

Regarding the updates on Application pages, NLK will send an email to all SMEs asking for updates and changes concerning the games and applications on a bimonthly basis. The toolkit page is being updated on demand: any change must be communicated to NLK by UMA. ICL will also provide additional information about the toolkit and applications **updates** which could be relevant for the website.

In addition, NLK will report the Diss/Com activity in a public document; this will also contain the detected bugs and the modifications.

3.1.1 Updates and modifications

The following sections formed the original website before M4 (Aug, 2014):

- Home: www.3d-tune-in.eu
- About: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/about>
 - Objectives, approach and impact: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/about/h2020-objectives-approach>
 - Consortium: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/about/consortium>
- News (blog): <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/news>
- Applications [UPDATED DURING Y1Q3]: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/applications>
 - MusiClarity: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/applications/hearing-aid-musical-listening>
 - Hearing Aid Tuner: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/applications/elderly-hearing-aid>
 - Dartanan: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/applications/hearing-aid-children-gamification>
 - Fallen Angel: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/applications/hearing-educational-games>
 - AudGam PRO: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/hearing-aids-calibration-game>
- Open Access Research Data: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/open-access-research-data-1>
- Resources: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/downloads>
 - Project materials: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/h2020-3dtunein-materials>

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- Project Public Deliverables: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/Deliverables>
- Audio Demos: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/audiodemos-hearing-aid-loss>
- 3D Tune-In presentation (English, Spanish and Italian): <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/animation>
- Questionnaire for hearing aid users: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/node/85>

3.1.2 Website modifications and updates from M4 (Aug, 2014) to M18 (Oct, 2016):

- **Introductory Video and Audio Demos:** during Y1-Q3, ICL and NLK have invested relevant time and resources to record and create a video to explain how the hearing aids could help people with hearing loss to improve their lives. In addition, three introductory videos, available in English, Italian, and Spanish, have been designed, created and uploaded. This high-value dissemination content can be found on the *Resources > Audio demonstrations* (<http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/node/67>); also, the videos can be found at *Resources > 3D Tune-In presentation* (English, Spanish and Italian): <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/animation>.
- A new page, called *Related EU Projects*, linked from the main header menu, was published at <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/gamification-eu-projects>
- Public deliverables are continuously being updated on the *Resources > Project Public Deliverables* page: <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/Deliverables>
- **Applications** pages were updated in January 2016, in accordance to the current Future Scenarios specified in the D1.1. (More information at <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/applications>)

New pages will be linked in the main menu, as sub-menu items below Applications, instead of the previous ones. The future applications and videogames to be developed by all SME partners are explained on the website, including some screenshots, sketches and concept-game charts where it is needed. The Applications subpages will be regularly updated as the project advances.

- Project materials are being regularly uploaded to the website on *Resources > project materials*, at <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/h2020-3dtunein-materials>
- Format issues, typos and bugs are weekly checked by NLK and the D&C Team in accordance with the procedures specified above.
- With regard to Google Analytics statistics, a spam filter was developed. Spam traffic could distort the statistics and the impact assessment on the website. Although *spam* emails did not affect the quality of the website's contents – because comments and internal interaction is not currently allowed – the filter facilitates the demographic and traffic analysis.

3.1.3 News section and blog

The blog is being regularly updated: some mechanisms were implemented to assure a regular flow of interesting contents. From M4 to M18, 19 news have been published on the website, hosted at <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/news>

3.1.4 Upcoming updates

In the short-term, two new subpages are going to be published: one referring to the 3D Tune-In Toolkit, and another specifically dedicated to scientific dissemination, containing articles published in journals and conference papers.

3.1.5 Results and Website Statistics.

Understandably, summer resulted the most challenging season of all (lower access to the website). Moreover, the navigation patterns observed were erratic and did not follow any specific trend.

3.1.5.1 Traffic flow

The following charts (Figure 2 and Table 3) show the traffic flow to the website, expressed as the number of sessions every week. A session is a group of interactions that take place on the website within a given time frame.

From M4 to M18, 9711 sessions were opened.

Table 4: Sessions (M4-M18)

Week	Sessions	Week	Sessions	Week	Sessions
1	158	21	192	42	175
2	284	22	252	43	138
3	232	23	304	44	121
4	56	24	246	45	267
5	69	25	318	46	242
6	73	26	218	47	212
7	96	27	259	48	388
8	104	28	78	49	204
9	89	29	136	50	125
10	97	30	84	51	151
11	62	31	118	52	220
12	101	32	113	53	219
13	80	33	80	54	220
14	107	34	107	55	176
15	141	35	124	56	158
16	75	36	80	57	163
17	207	37	86	58	158
18	219	38	102	59	235
19	229	39	110	60	152
20	201	40	151	61	178
		41	125	62	182

Figure 2: Sessions (M1-M18)

3.1.5.2 *Most viewed contents*

The most viewed content is the homepage, as expected. However, homepages commonly have a higher bounce rate than some other pages. Bounce rate represents the percentage of visitors who enter the site and then leave ("bounce") rather than continuing on to view other pages within the same site. The following table shows the bounce rate:

Table 5: bounce rates

	Title (Content)	Visits	Time (average)	Bounce rate
1	Welcome to 3D Tune-In	8.292	0:02:12	75,81 %
2	News	557	0:00:57	36,36 %
3	Objectives, Approach and Impact	351	0:02:31	55,56 %
4	About the Project	340	0:02:22	55,56 %
5	Consortium	318	0:01:50	35,71 %
6	Do you use Hearing Aids? Tell us about yourself!	292	0:06:05	59,23 %
7	Open Access Research Data	290	0:01:04	29,17 %
8	Project Materials	288	0:01:02	54,55 %
9	Project Public Deliverables	247	0:01:38	44,44 %
10	3D Tune-In Applications	204	0:01:19	59,09 %

The bounce rate on pages related with content considered "interesting" is low, and the time spent reading and exploring each page is well defined. The pages and articles are brief and very specific, so the time spent is adequate to the contents to be viewed by the users.

NLK invested relevant efforts for improving the Search Engine Optimisation, as well as the Social Media activities. Table 6 shows the results of this strategy:

Table 6: Acquisition channels

Channel	Sessions	New users	Pageviews/session
Organic Search (e.g., Google, Bing...)	4.378	3.358	1,6
Referral and social (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn)	2.800	2.206	1,43
Direct (e.g., from newsletters)	2.025	1.331	2,92

Social Media represent a very important channel for disseminating the project outcomes and news, but the *page-views per session* referring to organic searches (i.e. searches directly, from Google or from any other search engine) show an excellent performance. Users from organic searches viewed 1,6 pages per session. Direct traffic, mainly from newsletters, seems to have the highest *page-views/sessions* rate, because the targeted users are explicitly interested in the project and related topics

3.1.5.3 *Demographic information*

Table 7 shows the most relevant demographic information as provided by Google Analytics.

Table 7: Demographic information

Age range	
18 -24	31,96%
25-34	23%
35-44	28,57%
45-54	9,20%
55-64	3,39%
>65	3,87%
Sex ³	
Female	24,20%
Male	75,80%

3.1.6 Ethics

The following ethics issues must be taken into account when publishing photos (taken during an event, conference or fair) on the website and/or Social Media channels.

- When an underage individual is photographed, and the picture is published on the website or Social Media channels, her/his face must always be blurred, with no exceptions.
- Adult individuals who are not directly involved in the project have the right to control the use of their name and image, if these are in the dissemination materials. As a consequence, a written authorization is always needed, especially when the individual could be classified as a part of a vulnerable group. Otherwise, their faces must be blurred.
- With regards to people directly involved in the project, If an individual does not desire to appear in photos which could be published, he/she must warn the WP5 leader and the Coordinator

3.2 Project materials

A set of leaflets and other dissemination materials have been produced and updated accordingly to the project outcomes. The whole set of project materials can be found in the *Resources* page, at <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/downloads>

3.2.1 Videos

Due to the “content marketing-like” strategy, the website includes presentation videos, and will include multimedia material showing the main achievements of the project. These videos are continuously disseminated in our YouTube channel, as well as the social networks.

³ While the differences between gender and sex have been taken into account within the project since the beginning, unfortunately, Google Analytics allows to track only different genders. The Dissemination and Communication leader, the Ethics coordinator and the Project coordinator always take into consideration the ethics concerns regarding gender issues.

Figure 3: Introductory video to the 3DTI project - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dtzhiA5Xnvs>

Figure 4: Reasons for using hearing aids - <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/audiodemos-hearing-aid-loss> (hosted on YouTube)

Figure 5: Animation (Spanish, English and Italian) - <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/animation> (also hosted on YouTube)

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3.2.2 Branding

The project has a corporate image to keep a uniform look and feel in all dissemination material. This includes the 3D Tune-In logo, presentation templates, document templates, etc. All outlets make use of the same, professionally designed branding style, ensuring a uniform and professional appearance of the projects dissemination materials

Figure 6: 3D Tune-In logos

Two project logos have been created, as shown in Figure 6. Partners are advised to use the one on the left, and the one on the right only if it needs to be used on a dark background. During the third quarter of 2015, the Dissemination and Communication leader established a uniform guide of style for these outlets and a quality assurance procedure. The main background colour should be white, and the basic corporative colours are the following:

■ #333333

■ #0a3f71 ■ #004b7c
■ #1f8290 ■ #88bab9
 ■ #76abdc

Some other colours are also allowed:

■ #8bb236	
■ #dfa33a	■ #e0b8a3
■ #501f7f	■ #d38605
■ #a6121b	■ #b88b19
■ #5676b4	■ #f0d4aa

All materials produced within the project have to use Arial typographies or Sans Serif, if Arial is not available.

3.2.3 Posters, Banner and Roll-ups

During these months, 9 printable dissemination materials have been produced, all of them available on the website.

Table 6: Project Materials and link to public repositories.

Leaflet	http://3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/leaflet-definitive.pdf
Banner	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/banner_desk-definitive.pdf
Roll-up	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/roll-up-definitive%20%281%29.pdf
Press kit: academia	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/General%20presskit%20leaflet.pdf
Press kit: general society	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/General%20presskit%20leaflet.pdf
Press kit: general society - Spanish version	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/General%20%28Espa%C3%B1ol%29%20-%203D%20Tune-In%20%283D%20games%20for%20TUNing%20and%20lEarning%20about%20hearing%20aids%29.pdf
Dartanan Banner	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/Dartano%20Banner.pdf
Dartanan Cover	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/Dartano%20flyer-cover.pdf
Dartatan Roll-up	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/Dartano%20roll-up.pdf

Hearing loss is an inevitable part of the ageing process from around 25-30 years old. As the average age of Europe's population is increasing, with expectations by 2050 of two thirds being over 50 years old, demand for assistive hearing devices is also expected to grow.

Hearing Aid (HA) technology has dramatically advanced in the last 25 years, since the commercialization of the first digital hearing aid. Nevertheless, this technological advancement is not always accessible or appreciated by the hearing impaired population. The majority of individuals with hearing aids use the device as if it was a standard analogue hearing aid, i.e. only for its amplification and equalization features, and new algorithms are under-used or not exploited to their full potential.

Hearing impairment in older adults can lead to frustration, low esteem, withdrawal and can affect social isolation. Further to these, in children, hearing loss may affect speech and language development which can impact academic achievement and future vocational choices.

Our goal

The goal of 3D Tune-In is to understand the issues of hearing loss and facilitate the successful exploitation of existing, overlooked or neglected functionalities of hearing devices through the novel use of 3D gaming technologies.

How

3D Tune-In brings together the relevant stakeholders from traditional gaming industries (Reactif, Narlika, XTeam, Narlika Studios), academic institutions (Imperial College London, De Montfort University, the University of Nottingham, the University of Málaga), a large European hearing aid manufacturer (3D Hearing) and hearing communities through Associations – Entre Cere, Hearing Link, Action Deafness, Accesibilidad y Personas Sordas and Ente Nazionale Sordi) to create a novel 3D toolkit and games tailored to different target groups.

Expected impact

The impact of 3D Tune-In is potentially wide ranging for economic and societal benefits. It is intended to open up new markets for the traditional game industry and 3D technologies. More importantly, 3D Tune-In hopes to greatly improve people's quality of life, and their interactions with other people and their surrounding environment, while increasing public awareness of the challenges of hearing loss.

Figure 7: Leaflet

Figure 8: Large Roll-up

Figure 9: Large Banner

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With a budget of €2,896,175 3D Tune-In is funded under Horizon 2020, the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union. The project is coordinated by Dr. Lorenzo Picinali from Imperial College London and has a duration of 36 months, until May 2018.

3D Tune-In (3D-games for TUNing and IEarNing about hearing aids) brings together relevant stakeholders from traditional gaming industries, academic institutes, a large European hearing aid manufacturer and hearing communities to produce digital games in the field of hearing aid technologies and hearing loss in children and older adults, addressing social inclusion, generating new markets and creating job opportunities.

Scientific Dissemination & Research (Links)

- 3D Tune-In presentation at the [EUROPEAN CONFERENCE](#)
- [Hearing Journal publication on 3D Tune-In project](#)
- [Project Public Deliverables](#)

Useful links and Resources

- [Presentation video \(English\)](#)
- [Audio demonstration](#)
- How hearing loss can impair music and speech listening
- [Outcomes and metrics to be developed during 3D Tune-In project](#)

Project Videos

You can view these videos directly over the image of the link

3D Tune-In video presentation (English)

In this case, there is no specific "visual calibration" of a hearing aid yet... this part of what we are working within the 3D Tune-In project

3D Tune-In hearing loss and hearing aids utility demonstration video

Over 50 million people in Europe currently suffer from hearing loss, and due to an ageing population this number is likely to continue to increase. While hearing aid (HA) technologies have been immensely advanced in the last 25 years, people's perception and use of these devices have changed very little.

Imperial College London, The University of Nottingham, De Montfort University, ReSound, Reactify, and other partners.

Facebook.com/3DTuneIn, Twitter.com/3DTUNEIN, LinkedIn.com/company/3DTune-In-3D-games-for-TUNing-and-IEarNing

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 844021.

Figure 10 - Press kits (Academia, left; General society, right)

HEARING AID CALIBRATION/ASSESSMENT FOR CHILDREN

The audiologist told Aaron's Mum that he may need her help to set up the game initially. Dartanan uses a simple gamification technique: unlock a new mini-game after progressing through each level. The main game has three levels, and is fun, fast and colourful and is used to engage the players.

There is the potential for an infinite number of minigames that train players on how to calibrate the different settings of their HA and use this learning to progress through the different levels. This division is designed to develop a leisure game that also contains serious games: children can play the main game with their friends and parents, and the mini-games can be adapted to different target devices for training and learning purposes.

Imperial College London, The University of Nottingham, De Montfort University, ReSound, Reactify, and other partners.

Figure 11: Dartanan application (XTEAM) materials

3.3 Newsletter

A newsletter has been produced every three months, collecting information such as reached milestones, achieved results and events of special interest. The consortium has sent 4 newsletters: the first one – the introductory newsletter – was aimed at presenting the project to its target audience. The subsequent newsletters have the objective to widely disseminate the most important news.

3.3.1 Introductory Newsletter:

[http://us12.campaign-archive2.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=d7ef511b53&e=\[UNIQID\]](http://us12.campaign-archive2.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=d7ef511b53&e=[UNIQID])

The introductory newsletter was sent on the 4th of March 2016, to 59 recipients. Its open rate⁴ was 28.9% and the click rate⁵ 3.6%. The 24-hour performance shows that the first hour is critical to ensure a good spread. This newsletter was sent on a Friday; having observed its results, the D&C Team decided not to send further newsletters on a Thursday or Friday.

3.3.2 #1 Newsletter:

[http://us12.campaign-archive1.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=14d3a961b0&e=\[UNIQID\]](http://us12.campaign-archive1.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=14d3a961b0&e=[UNIQID])

This had the definitive format agreed for newsletters, and was comprised of news and calls for volunteers. The #1 newsletter was sent on the 22nd of March to 96 recipients; the open and click rates were slightly improved compared to the introductory one: 32.9 and 5.4% respectively.

3.3.3 #2 Newsletter

[http://us12.campaign-archive1.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=14d3a961b0&e=\[UNIQID\]](http://us12.campaign-archive1.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=14d3a961b0&e=[UNIQID])

The second newsletter was sent on the 11th of May to 96 recipients; the #2 newsletter improved on the results of previous releases: the open rate was 37% and the click rate 6.5%. Also, the subscribers with more opens were not involved in the consortium.

3.3.4 #3 Newsletter

[http://us12.campaign-archive2.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=04e2357d54&e=\[UNIQID\]](http://us12.campaign-archive2.com/?u=0f4984c9b06b4c09408a5ffdc&id=04e2357d54&e=[UNIQID])

Newsletter 3 was released on the 21st of September to 98 recipients, and has had an open rate of 39.2% and a click rate of 7.1%.

3.4 Section 4.4: Press releases and non-peer reviewed articles

Public documents are released as a means for providing regular updates to the wider public about the current status and position of the project. From M1 to M18, 10 press releases and non-peer reviewed articles were published.

Table 7: Press releases and non-peer reviewed articles

Type	Content	Date and place	Targets	URL
Non-peer reviewed article	CORDIS WIRE	26/06/2015	Research	http://cordis.europa.eu/news/rcn/125017_en.html
Press Release	Audiology News World	07/08/2015	Audiologists	http://www.audiology-worldnews.com/profession/1406-3d-tune-in-facilitating-hearing-aid-use-through-gaming

⁴ Open rate indicates how many people opened the email sent out.

⁵ Click rate measures the ratio of clicks inside the email; thus, the number of times a click is made is divided by the total impressions. Impressions are the number of times that the email was sent (3DTI contact list has 96 people, so there are at least 96 impressions, although users could re-send the emails to others)

Press Release	La Voce di Rovigo	28/09/2015	General public	Printed
Non-peer reviewed article	IneveryCrea article	19/10/2015 (Website, Spain)	Educational community	http://ineverycrea.net/comunidad/ineverycrea/recurso/3d-tunein-deficits-auditivos-en-el-aula/388c0e5e-ced8-4010-8b05-51a69e8dfc02
Press release	Euro VR translated in Italian	20/11/2015	Audiologists	Printed
Non-peer reviewed article	Mercury (website)	15/11/2016	Audiologists	http://www.mercurydiagnostics.it/
Non-peer reviewed publication	Escuela20 (website)	12/11/2015	Educational community	http://www.escuela20.com/gamificacion-educacion-edtech/articulos-y-actualidad/para-que-sirve-la-gamificacion-en-el-mundo-real_3969_42_5579_0_1_in.html
Non-peer reviewed article	European Digital Agenda: mention	02/12/2015	Industry players	http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/european-commission-supports-research-and-innovation-technologies-break-down-barriers-people
Press Release	Audiology Infos: "Usage Gli Apparecchi Acustici"	03/03/2016	Audiologists	Printed
Non-peer reviewed article	Tecniche di gamification e sistemi di intelligenza artificiale applicati alle protesi acustiche	04/03/2016	Industry players	http://www.triwi.it/3dtunein/

3.5 Section 4.5: Academic Dissemination

Scientific dissemination is supported by publications in peer reviewed journals and scientific conferences. So far, partners have been involved in ten scientific dissemination activities. Table 8 summarizes the type of dissemination event or activity and its location and date.

Table 8: Scientific dissemination activities

Type	Event	Date and place	Target Audience
Conference	IDETC/CIE 2015	2/8/2015-5/8/2015. Boston (USA)	Research
Conference	EuroVr Conference 2015	15/10/2015-16/10/2015. Lecco (Italy)	Research
Article	Journal Publication in "Hearing Journal" – "3D Tune-In: 3D Games for Tuning and Learning About Hearing aids"	02/02/2016	Research
Conference	POSTER: Workshop on Auditory Neuroscience, Cognition and Modelling at Queen Mary University,	17/02/2016. London (UK)	Research
Conference	3D-game for TUNing hEarlNg aids (3D Tune-In): Connecting Hearing Aid Stakeholders with Digital	16/03/2016. Nottingham	Research

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IEarnIng about hearing aids

	Game Designers	(UK)	
Conference	Seminar titled “Applications with Binaural Audio” (Institute of Sound and Vibration Research (ISVR) at the University of Southampton)	16/2/2016. Southampton (UK)	Research
Conference	Imperial MedTech Links event: Wearables, Behaviour and Data - Presentation titled “Using Virtual Reality (VR) to improve hearing aid effectiveness”, and demo of the HRTF adaptation test.	23/3/2016. London (UK)	Research
Conference	Annual congress of Italian Society of otorhinolaryngology	25/5/2016- 28/5/2016. Rome (Italy)	Medical doctors, audiologists
Conference	140th AES Convention / AES Paris 2016 - Audio Engineering Society	4/6/2016- 7/6/2016. Paris (France)	Academia; industry players. Audio technology, engineering and VR.
Conference	The 12th International Conference on Intelligent Environments - IE'16 - 12-16th September 2016, London	12/9/2016- 16/9-2016. London (UK)	Academia; researchers; scientific community.

Table 10 details the scientific publications within the 3DTI Project, including published and *in press* outcomes. The last item refers to a PhD thesis which is expected to be completed and submitted by 2019.

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Table 9: Scientific dissemination – publications

Type of activity	Title of Scientific Publication	DOI	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number, date	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant pages	Public & Private participation	Peer review	Is/will open access be provided for this publication
Article in Journal	3D Tune-In: 3D Games for Tuning and Learning About Hearing Aids	10.1097/01.HJ.0000481810.74569.d8	ISSN: 0745-7472; Online ISSN: 2333-6218	Eastgate, R., Picinali, L., Patel, H., & D'Cruz, M.	Hearing Journal	Volume 69 - Issue 4 - pp 30,32	Wolters Kluwer		2016	pp.30-32	No	Yes	Yes - Gold OA
Publication in conference proceeding/ workshop	3D-Tune-In: the use of 3D visuals and sound to facilitate use of hearing devices.	N/A	N/A	Picinali, L., D'Cruz, M. & Simone, L.	EuroVR 2015	N/A	European Association for Virtual Reality	Lecco	2015	N/A	No	Yes	Yes – Green OA
Publication in conference proceeding/ workshop	3D Tune-In: The Use of 3D Sound and Gamification to Aid Better Adoption of Hearing Aid Technologies	N/A	N/A	Levtov, Y., Picinali, L., D'Cruz, M. & Simeone, L.10	Conference paper at 140th Audio Engineering Society Convention	N/A	Audio Engineering Society	Paris	2016	N/A	No	Yes	Yes – Green OA
Publication in conference proceeding/ workshop	3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and	N/A	N/A	Picinali, L., D'Cruz, M. &	The 12th International Conference on 1	N/A	N/A	London	2016	N/A	No	Yes	Yes – Green OA

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Type of activity	Title of Scientific Publication	DOI	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number, date	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant pages	Public & Private participation	Peer review	Is/will open access be provided for this publication
	IearnIng about hearing aids			Simone, L.	Intelligent Environments - IE'16								
Conference Poster	A mobile-based platform for evaluating localisation of virtual sound sources (poster demo)	N/A	N/A	Mark Steadman and Lorenzo Picinali	Workshop on Auditory Neuroscience, Cognition and Modelling	Wed 17th February 2016	QMUL, London	Queen Mary University, London	2016	N/A	No	No	Yes – Green OA
Thesis/dissertation	<i>Still in progress: not submitted, not titled</i>	N/A	N/A	Maria Cuevas Rodriguez	University of Malaga				2019 [expected]				

3.6 Joint activities with other EU projects

The 3D Tune-In consortium has built relations and alliances with five EU-Funded projects. This contributes to ensure the sustainability and the transfer of best practices in the field of dissemination and communication; in the short-term, we plan to participate in some joint scientific dissemination activities. The D&C Team started the prospective search for alliances in December 2015. The related EU projects are detailed at <http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/gamification-eu-projects>

These projects are

- NO ONE LEFT BEHIND: Gamification for inclusive formal learning environments. Website: <http://no1leftbehind.eu/>
- PROSOCIAL LEARN: Gamification of prosocial learning for increased youth inclusion and academic achievement. Website: <http://prosociallearn.eu/>
- RAGE: Boosting games development for education and training in Europe. Website: <http://rageproject.eu/>
- BEACONING: Gameful personalized learning. Website: <http://www.beaconing.eu/>
- MOBILE AGE: Inclusion of seniors in digital services. Website: <http://www.mobile-age.eu/>

Regular meetings are taking places between the 3DTI coordinator and partners of these projects, aiming at collaborating towards maximising results and impact of the project.

3.7 Public presentations at fairs and events

In a similar way to that for the scientific community, project results are being disseminated in fairs and events focused on the video games industry, including independent developers and bigger publishers. The partners – specifically SMEs – have attended 17 workshops or trade-fairs, as detailed in Table 11.

Table 10: Workshop, fairs and trade events

Event	Date and place	Target Audience
Game Conference Zurich	1/07/2015 Milano (Italy)	Research
Game Over - Indie developers fair and party (Milano)	19/9/2015-20/9/2015. Milano (Italy)	Industry players
F.I.R.S.T. 2015 (Festival Per L'Innovazione, La Ricerca, Il Sociale e Il Territorio)	25/9/2015-26/9/2015. Padova (Italy)	Research
Imperial Fringe	24/9/2015. London (UK)	Research
ROBRICK fair	31/10/2015. Rovigo (Italy)	General public
Generali Innovation Challenge (Microsoft)	17/11/2015. Rovigo (Italy)	Industry players
IV CONGRESSO NAZIONALE Palacongressi di Rimini	20/11/2015-22/11/2016. Rimini (Italy)	Elderly end-users
48th RUMSX (Valencia)	2/12/2015. Castellón (Spain)	Industry players
3D Tune-In used as a project work at the Politecnico di Milano	18/1/2016. Milano	Other
SMAU Workshop - New opportunities for the development of technologies for disability and	11/03/2016. Padova (Italy)	Industry players

quality of life		
Mathematics and rehabilitation	19/3/2016. PiGreco Rovigo (Italy)	Other
Math ideas	20/3/2016. Padova (Italy)	Other
Bologna Children’s Book Fair	04/04/2016. Bologna (Italy)	Educational community
Imperial Festival 2016	7/5/2016-8/5/2016. London	Academics, industry and general public
NordicGame 2016	20/5/2016. Malmo (Sweden)	
Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino 2016	12/5/2016-16/5/2016. Torino (Italy)	Journalists, education, publishers. General society.
SIFEL (Italian Society of Phoniatics and Logopedics speech therapy) Congress	23/6/2016-25/6/2016. Catania (Italy)	Medical doctors, audiologists

3.8 Social media activity

Creating a large online community is an effective method for exploitation of project results. A variety of social media platforms (e.g. YouTube, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn) have been considered to further enhance the communication of the project and its results. As seen in Section 4.1., social media channels have a great impact on dissemination of results, being an important source of web-traffic, and a new engaging way to involve the society, the civil society, main players and professional and academic communities.

3.8.1 Strategy

The Social Media plan was updated in September 2015. However, it must be modified as the project advances to adapt the content and methodology to each phase objective s (Section 3 – Overall Strategy).

3.8.1.1 Objectives

- **To provide a regular flow of information** about the project and its results to both industry and academic community.
- **To promote results and benefits of the project to target audiences.** Key audiences will be defined as the project develops, but initial groups will be found within the games industry and hearing communities.

3.8.1.2 Social Media Channels

From M4 to M18, a Facebook page, Twitter account, a Youtube channel and a LinkedIn group were created and regularly updated:

Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/3DTuneIn>)

Purpose: connects with stakeholders and relevant researchers. Allows segmental advisory if needed.

Uses: spreading news and networking. Content curation.

Twitter <https://twitter.com/3dtunein>

Purpose: Twitter is a very ephemeral channel, but it allows conversation, networking using a collaborative approach and gets information about similar initiatives. It also works as a newsfeed.

Uses: Newsfeed, networking.

YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXldMvJQjdZ0bn aovEXciLg>

Purpose: Share multimedia dissemination content with stakeholders and researchers worldwide (slides, speeches, events, successful use cases, etc.).

Uses: Repository of multimedia dissemination material.

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8409367>

Purpose: Disseminate the project outcomes among EU researchers, special education teachers and therapists, etc.

3.8.1.3 Vision statements

- **Knowledge transfer.** Apply technologies and techniques normally used in traditional gaming applications to a non-leisure application such as HA demonstration and calibration.
- **Gamification.** Successfully employ a gamification approach for tasks (demonstration and calibration of HA) which have never been related to games.
- **Game-centred.** Make the gaming part of 3D Tune-In fully integrated into the system in a way that it is not just a useful, but the essence of the application.
- **Transferrable.** Make the experience using 3D Tune-In applications actually reflect the real world, and to work as a real-world experience. The HA calibration performed through VR tools within 3D Tune-In, will be successfully usable in real-world scenarios.
- **Affordable.** Make the 3D Tune-In tools affordable, both regarding cost and usability.

3.8.1.4 Targets, channels and communication

Table 11: Overall strategy and minimum required interaction

Social Media Tool	Main target/s (organized by priority)	Communication	Frequency
Facebook	People with hearing aids Industry & IT developers and providers Audiologists, physicians, etc. Special Education.	Links (website, external resources) Images and photography show great impact (events, screenshots, etc.) Video (YouTube)	1 post per week (min). Not connected to Twitter feed. Check primetime (1M): a priori, 20.00pm
Twitter	Special Education Industry & IT developers and providers Audiologists, physicians, etc. People with hearing aids	News and links to website or YouTube and external resources. Conversation and community building	4 posts per week Check primetime (3M). Standard: 12:00, 17:00, 18:00, 20:30
YouTube	Industry & IT developers and providers Special Education. Audiologists, physicians, etc.	Videos: presentations, speeches, slides, use-cases.	On demand.
LinkedIn	Industry & IT developers and providers Special Education.	Newsfeed, networking.	1 post per month

3.8.1.5 Social media content procedures

- The procedure does not include an approval process for all content

- A content removal procedure has been agreed for inappropriate content. Involved partners in charge of Social Media channels may NOT post the following:
 - a) Duplicate content
 - b) Twitter feed clones (Facebook and Twitter are different: duplicating the Twitter feed is a **malpractice**)
 - c) Third-party advertising. If a SME/freelance uses the Facebook page for advertising his/her games, etc. it will be deleted, and the user will be blocked.
 - d) Content intended for an adult audience or violent images, videos or text.
 Privacy strategies or procedures are in place to ensure the security of personal information will be in line with Data Protection Regulations for each country involved.
- No specific procedures have been established on accepting new followers.

3.8.2 Performance and statistics.

While, currently, the D&C are testing the trial version of IBM Watson Analytics, the following measurements were taken from LikeAnalyser, Sociograph.io and Cycle.

3.8.2.1 Facebook

Currently, the Facebook fan page has 67 likes, growing at a rate of 4.7% per month. The most important rates are the PTAT (*People Talking About This*) and the Engagement rate: these are 14 and 20.9% respectively⁶.

The fanpage managers publish 0.58 posts per day on average and there are 2 interactions per post. Regarding the types of posts, 4.2% are images (without links or any other interactive resource), 4.2% are videos and 91.7% are links; the fans seems to respond best to links, especially links posted between 12.00pm and 15.00pm (GMT).

The posts often have more than 100 characters to improve the search engine optimization and the engagement of these. Up to date, 145 posts have been published, and although there are 67 members, there are 87 “likers”: so there are more people than members who interact with the content.

The Facebook audience shows interest for hearing loss, both tips for quotidian life and research in this field. Images, pictures and photos also have a great performance. Top posts, since the beginning (“all-time posts”) are detailed in Table 13.

Table 12: All-time top posts

	id	Description	URL	Time	Likes	Comments	Shares	Type
1	16724862529 80377_18022 06140008387	End-users survey: Spanish version <i>Advertised traffic, non-organic</i>	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1802206140008387	2016-07-19T10:11:00+0000	56	0	1	link

⁶ Source: LikeAnalyser.

2	16724862529 80377_17087 98979349104	Málaga meeting post and photo	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1708798979349104	2015-10-30T12:47:52+0000	9	0	2	photo
3	16724862529 80377_17080 36966091972	Málaga meeting pictures	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1708036966091972	2015-10-27T09:50:48+0000	8	0	1	photo
4	16724862529 80377_17433 54192560249	Most deaf and hearing impaired children can attend mainstream schools with adequate support	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1743354192560249	2016-02-26T11:01:00+0000	7	0	0	link
5	16724862529 80377_17082 73746068294	Málaga meeting pictures	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1708273746068294	2015-10-28T09:50:53+0000	7	0	1	photo
6	16724862529 80377_17005 75343504801	The development of #HearingAids over time	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1700575343504801	2015-10-07T17:10:01+0000	7	0	0	photo
7	16724862529 80377_17692 51893303812	Nottingham meeting pictures	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1769251893303812	2016-04-27T06:38:00+0000	6	0	0	photo
8	16724862529 80377_17433 54675893534	The Hearing Journal, a well-known publication in hearing healthcare, has published a paper about our project.	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1743354675893534	2016-02-26T09:03:00+0000	6	0	0	link
9	16724862529 80377_17301 08177218184	Communication Tips For All From Someone With Hearing Loss	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1730108177218184	2016-01-15T11:17:01+0000	6	0	0	link
10	16724862529 80377_17160 92218619780	Experts have published in The Lancet a list of the most urgent priorities for researching mild to moderate #hearingLoss	https://www.facebook.com/1672486252980377/posts/1716092218619780	2015-11-27T11:53:31+0000	6	0	0	link

3.8.2.2 Twitter

Twitter seems to be the most cost-effective channel for the 3D Tune-In consortium. Currently, @3DTuneIn account has 101 followers, and the interactions, visits and followers are increasing at a sustainable rate, although summer has required a greater effort than spring. Table 14 shows the overall progress.

Table 13: Twitter performance

	2015					2016								
	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
Tweets	1	3	4	4	12	13	15	18	12	23	11	24	28	18

Profile visits	46	245	200	139	102	155	100	103	151	83	103	179	152	91
Mentions	1	3	2	5	9	6	5	3	18	2	3	6	4	2
Impressions	28	1541	812	6400	1765	3244	3454	3286	2197	4234	3495	3724	3828	3064

The overall effect of increasing tweets publication is not so clear at this stage: it seems that tweets publications have not had a real impact on profile visits; profile visits are the most critical factor to increase active followers in Twitter.

Figure 12: Tweets and Profile visits.

3.8.2.3 Socio-demographic analysis: Twitter and Facebook

The audience is interested in tech news, business and news, technology (63%), science news (58%), politics (52%), books, news and general information (38%) and entrepreneurship (35%). 55% of them are males, and 45% are females. The vast majority of our followers and fans are aged between 35-44 years old (52%), followed by 25-34 years old group (27%). People over 55 years old only represent 3% of the total audience. More effort will be invested to reach the oldest age groups.

Although the Italian partners have invested great resources in their dissemination activity, the Italian audience represents less than 1% of the total audience. People from the United Kingdom represent 22% of the audience, 14% were from the United States, 12% from Germany and 11% from Spain. It is worth noting that the audience from Belgium (5%) is mainly represented by the main channels of communication put in place by the European Commission, among others, [@Horizon2020EU](https://twitter.com/Horizon2020EU)

3.8.2.4 LinkedIn

LinkedIn has a professional and academic-focused approach. Currently, 34 individuals have joined the group, 3D Tune-In (3D-games for TUNing and IEarnING about hearing aids) <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8409367>

Table 14: LinkedIn group - Geographical coverage

UK	10
Spain	12
Italy	4
Emirates	1
Sweden	1
Belgium	3
Germany	1
USA	2

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and lEarniNg about hearing aids

3.8.2.5 Youtube

The Youtube channel was created on the 15th of July 2015. Up to date, the total visualization time spent by the audience is 1112 minutes. Seven videos have been published. Our audience were from Italy (32%), UK (22%), Spain (9.8%), United States (5.7%) and Germany (3.4%). They visualized the videos on the website (74%); only 26% of total visualizations were accessed directly on Youtube.

Section 4. Dissemination activities

The following table shows the complete log of dissemination activities achieved by the partners from M1 to M18.

Table 15 Dissemination activities of the partners up to M18

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
DM.001	Diss/Com Materials	Leaflet	01/09/2015	All	http://3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/leaflet-definitive.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.002	Diss/Com Materials	Banner	01/09/2015	All	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/banner_desk-definitive.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.003	Diss/Com Materials	Roll-up	01/09/2015	All	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/roll-up-definitive%20%281%29.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.004	Diss/Com Materials	Introductory video to the 3DTI project	01/09/2015	Research	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dtzhiA5Xnvs	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.005	Diss/Com Materials	Hearing Aid utility: video	01/11/2015	End-users	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/audiodemos-hearing-aid-loss	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.006	Diss/Com Materials	Presskit: academia	15/01/2016	Research	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/General-%20presskit%20leaflet.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.007	Diss/Com Materials	Presskit: general society	15/01/2016	All	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/General-%20presskit%20leaflet.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.008	Diss/Com Materials	Presskit: general	01/02/2016	All	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/General%20%28Esp	N/A	Not available	N/A

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
	Materials	society - Spanish version			a%C3%B1o%29%20-%203D%20Tune-In%20%283D%20games%20for%20TUNing%20and%20IearnIng%20about%20hearing%20aids%29.pdf			
DM.009	Diss/Com Materials	Dartanan Banner	01/02/2016	End-users; industry players	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/Dartatano%20Banner.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.010	Diss/Com Materials	Dartanan Cover	01/02/2016	End-users; industry players	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/Dartatano%20flyer-cover.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.011	Diss/Com Materials	Dartanan Roll-up	01/02/2016	End-users; industry players	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/sites/default/files/articles/Dartatano%20roll-up.pdf	N/A	Not available	N/A
DM.012	Diss/Com Materials	Animation (Spanish, English, and Italian)	01/01/2016	All	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/animation	N/A	Not available	N/A
DA.001	Workshop/Fair	Game Conference Zurich	1/07/2015 Milan (Italy)	Research	N/A	Presentation of XTeam Software Solution and 3D Tune-In during the conference. Explained the project 3D Tune-In at the "Department of Culture" of Zurich	Not available	Developer, journalists, politicians, publisher
DA.002	Conference	IDETC/CIE 2015	2/8/2015-5/8/2015.	Research	http://www.asmeconferences.org/IDETC2015/	The video was displaying it on a loop on one of the screens at the conference	Not available	Academic

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
			Boston (USA)					
DA.003	Non-peer reviewed article	CORDIS WIRE	26/06/2015	Research	http://cordis.europa.eu/news/rcn/125017_en.html	N/A	Not available	EU projects public, researchers, developers,
DA.004	Press Release	Audiology World News	07/08/2015	Audiologists	http://www.audiology-worldnews.com/profession/1406-3d-tune-in-facilitating-hearing-aid-use-through-gaming	N/A	Not available	N/A
DA.005	Workshop/Fair	Game Over - Indie developers fair and party (Milano)	19/9/2015-20/9/2015. Milano (Italy)	Industry players	http://www.gameovermilano.tk/	N/A	Not available	Indie developers
DA.006	Workshop/Fair	F.I.R.S.T. 2015 (Festival Per L'Innovazione, La Ricerca, Il Sociale e Il Territorio)	25/9/2015-26/9/2015. Padova (Italy)	Research	http://padovafirst.it/	N/A	Not available	Economy, education, health and environment
DA.007	Press Release	La Voce di Rovigo	28/09/2015	General public	Printed	N/A	Not available	(Local newspaper). Main population

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
DA.008	Workshop/Fair	Imperial Fringe	24/9/2015. London (UK)	Research	http://www3.imperial.ac.uk/newsandeventspggrp/imperialcollege/eventssummary/event_21-7-2015-14-11-40	N/A	Not available	Academia
DA.009	Conference	EuroVr	15/10/2015-16/10/2015. Lecco (Italy)	Research	http://www.eurovr-association.org/conference2015/	Publication – (demo paper)	Not available	Scientific community
DA.010	Non-peer reviewed article	IneveryCrea article	19/10/2015 (Website, Spain)	Educational community	http://ineverycrea.net/comunidad/ineverycrea/recursos/3d-tunein-deficits-auditivos-en-el-aula/388c0e5e-ced8-4010-8b05-51a69e8dfc02	75 views	ineverycrea.net website review (source: OpenAdmin Tools); Page Rank: 7; Alexa Traffic Rank (Spain) : 14776; Alexa Traffic Rank (Worldwide): 357149; 5000-15000 single page views per day	Teachers (primary and secondary education, special needs education)
DA.011	Workshop/Fair	ROBRICK fair	31/10/2015 Rovrigo (Italy)	General public	http://www.robrick.it	New Future scenario with the use of Lego and Duplo brick.	7000 visitors	Society
DA.012	Workshop/Fair	Generali Innovation Challenge (Microsoft)	17/11/2015. Rovrigo (Italy)	Industry players	http://generali.skipsolabs.com	Generali Assicurazione	Visitors about 50. Manager of Generali and Microsoft (not only Italian, it is a European challenge, 3000+ startups). Television (TGCom) https://www.youtube.c	Industry, developers, start-up and seed phase companies.

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
							om/watch?v=i4QeD0L4mpY	
DA.013	Press release	Euro VR translated in Italian	20/11/2015	Audiologists	Printed	N/A	In press.	Audiologist and ENT. Riproduzione di suoni, visualizzazione e gamification 3D per facilitare l'utilizzo degli apparecchi acustici
DM.013	Diss/Com materials	Resized roll-up/italian	27/11/2015	Audiologists	Printed	Brochure holder, translated		Customers and end-users
DA.014	Communication Campaign	Brief Description of 3D Tune-In: email marketing campaign	15/10/2015	Audiologists	N/A	Newsletter/ mailing campaign	Email-marketing: impact reached about 7000	Customers
DA.015	Non-peer reviewed article	Mercury (website)	15/11/2016	Audiologists	http://www.mercurydiagnostics.it/	N/A	N/A	Audiologist and ENT
DA.016	Non-peer reviewed publication	Escuela20 (website)	12/11/2015	Educational community	http://www.escuela20.com/gamificacion-educacion-edtech/articulos-y-actualidad/para-que-sirve-la-gamificacion-en-el-mundo-real_3969_42_5579_0_1_in.html	Mention (among other gamification apps and projects)	Page views: 423	Education (teachers, SEN, etc.)
DA.017	Workshop/Fair	IV CONGRESSO NAZIONALE	20/11/2015-22/11/2016.	Elderly End users	http://www.cortegiustiziapopolare.it/	Euro VR translated and slightly modified (approved by the authors). Brief		Elderly end-users

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
		LE Palacongressi di Rimini	Rimini (Italy)			description by GN using public project information/material		
DA. 018	Workshop/Fair	48th RUMSX (Valencia)	2/12/2015. Castellón (Spain)	Industry players	http://www.aamsx.com/reuniones_ES.php	Leaflet exposed at the workshop. Indie developers	400 attendees.	n/a
DA. 019	Non-peer reviewed article	European Digital Agenda: mention (New)	02/12/2015	Industry players	http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/european-commission-supports-research-and-innovation-technologies-break-down-barriers-people	Mention, brief explanation, and link to the project site on CORDIS, among other projects based on gamification and functional diversity	No traffic data available (Alexa Traffic Rank: 802)	Society, academic peers, companies and SMEs
DA. 020	Workshop/Fair	3D Tune-In used as a project work at the Politecnico di Milano	18/1/2016. Milano	Other	http://www.3d-tune-in.eu/project-work-milan ; http://www.servicedesignmaster.com/design-pill2-gamification-healthcare.html	Other: Students	11 students; XX academic community members	
DA. 021	Article	Journal Publication in "Hearing Journal" – "3D Tune-In: 3D	02/02/2016	Research	http://journals.lww.com/thehearingjournal/blog/OnlineFirst/pages/post.aspx?PostID=6	Paper copy to follow once it is available	Online publication Alexa Rank: 10,701 Article/ Page Rank 5 – Website Daily Global Rank Trend 9,5K visitors	ISSN: 0745-7472; Online ISSN: 2333-6218; Frequency: 12 issues / year

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IEarNing about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
		Games for Tuning and Learning About Hearing Aids”						
DA.022	Conference	POSTER Workshop on Auditory Neuroscience, Cognition, and Modelling at Queen Mary University	17/02/2016. London (UK)	Research	Event: http://c4dm.eecs.qmul.ac.uk/wancm2016/ ; Annex: https://drive.google.com/open?id=0BzNWwaGq9fRZSzJ6R1V0NzZCaIE	Poster submitted	Not available	N/A
DA.023	Press Release	Audiology Infos: "Usage Gli Apparecchi Acustici"	03/03/2016	Audiologists	Printed	Printed version	Not available	N/A
DA.024	Conference	3D-game for TUNing hEarNing	16/03/2016. Nottingham	Research	N/A	Seminar held at National Institute for Health Research, Nottingham Hearing	Academics, researchers, and audiologists at the Nottingham Biomedical Research Unit	N/A

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and LEarnING about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
		aids (3D Tune-In): Connecting Hearing Aid Stakeholders with Digital Game Designers	(UK)			Biomedical Research Unit, UK		
DA.025	Workshop/Fair	SMAU Workshop - New opportunities for the development of technologies for disability and quality of life	11/03/2016. Padova (Italy)	Industry players	http://www.smau.it/padova16/schedules/nuove-opportunita-per-lo-sviluppo-di-tecnologie-per-la-disabilita-e-la-qualita-della-vita/	Journalist and IT professionals	Not available	N/A
DA.026	Workshop/Fair	"Mathematics and rehabilitation"	19/3/2016. PiGrecoro Vigoro (Italy)	Other	http://www.pigracorovigo.it/events/lutilizzo-della-matematica-nella-riabilitazione/	Journalists, students and physiotherapists (about 30 participants)	30 participants	N/A
DA.027	Workshop/Fair	Math ideas	20/3/2016.	Other	http://www.pigracorovigo.it/events/la-fiera-delle-math-idee/	Journalists, students and physiotherapists	300 attendees	N/A

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
			Padova (Italy)			(about 300 visitors)		
DA.028	Workshop/Fair	Bologna Children's Book Fair	04/04/2016. Bologna (Italy)	Educational community	http://www.bookfair.bolognafiere.it/en/programme/general-programme/5663.html	Education professionals.	Journalist (about 60 from 10 countries) and educators (45)	N/A
DA.029	Conference	Seminar titled "Applications with Binaural Audio"	16/2/2016. Southampton (UK)	Research	http://www.southampton.ac.uk/engineering/news/seminars/2016/02/16-lorenzo-picinali.page	Institute of Sound and Vibration Research (ISVR) at the University of Southampton, UK	25 attendees	N/A
DA.030	Conference	Imperial MedTech Links event: Wearables, Behaviour and Data - Presentation titled "Using Virtual Reality (VR) to improve hearing aid effectiveness"	23/3/2016. London	Research	http://www.imperial.ac.uk/medtech/events/	Target: academia & industry players	The seminar was attended by approximately 50 delegates from the academic sector and 50 from the industry sector.	N/A

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
		ess", and demo of the HRTF adaptation test.						
DA.031	Non-peer reviewed article	Tecniche di gamificazione e sistemi di intelligenza artificiale applicati alle protesi acustiche	04/03/2016	Industry players	http://www.triwu.it/3dtunein/	As a result, from SMAU Workshop (DA.025)	Google PageRank 4; Alexa: 5235151	N/A
DA.032	Workshop/Fair	Imperial Festival 2016	7/5/2016-8/5/2016. London	Academics, industry and general public	http://www.imperial.ac.uk/festival/about/festival-2016/events-programme/	Demo of the HRTF adaptation test, and general presentation on the 3DTI project (stand with flyers)	About 20,000 visitors attended the festival. Mainly general public and students, a large number of academics and alumni, and several representatives of industries.	N/A
DA.033	Workshop/Fair	NordicGame 2016	20/5/2016. Malmö (Sweden)		http://nordicgame.com/registration-opens-for-nordic-game-2016/	1.200 indie developers / journalists / graphic designers / musicians	N/A	Discussion about the 3DTI Toolkit
DA.034	Conference	Annual congress	25/5/2016-	Medical doctors,	www.sio2016roma.eu	Italian version of the leaflet, project video	Target audience: -ENT specialists	Photos of the stand with 3D video, project's materials

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnIng about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
		of Italian Society of otorhinolaryngology	28/5/2016. Rome (Italy)	audiologists		subtitled in Italian, brochure holder to display the 3D with IQ code, project slides in Italian summarising projects goals, partners, apps)	(otolaryngologist) 80% - Vestibologists 15% - Audiologists 5%, Exhibiting industry players - HAS manufacturers, medical devices manufacturers, pharmaceutical industries. Attendees: total to SEO: 1200-1300; client contacted by GN Mercury: 220	distributed in two stands
DA. 035	Workshop/Fair	Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino 2016	12/5/2016-16/5/2016. Torino (Italy)	Journalists, Education, publishers. General society.	http://www.salone libro.it/it/espositori/elenco-espositori-2016.html?id=22&view=elem&cid=13045	N/A	Journalists (20) Educators (15) Publisher (5) Visitors (70)	http://www.salone libro.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=14805:3d-games-for-tuning-and-learning-about-hearing-aids-12363&catid=286:2016&Itemid=143
DA. 036	Conference	AES 2016	4/6/2016-7/6/2016. Paris	Academia; industry players. Audiotechnology, engineering and VR.	http://www.aes.org/events/140/	N/A	Europe's largest gathering of audio professionals from around the globe. More than 1000 attendees	N/A
DA. 037	Workshop/Fair	SIFEL (Italian Society of	23/6/2016-25/6/	Medical doctors, audiology	N/A	N/A	Prevalence of doctors and specialist in speech therapy and Phoniatry.	N/A

3D Tune-In: 3D-games for TUNing and IearnINg about hearing aids

Control number	Type of Activity	Content brief summary	Date and place	Target Audience	URL	Comments	Impact indicators	More information
		Phoniatics and Logopedics speech therapy) Congress	2016. Catania (Italy)	ists			Audiologists. About 300 participants. 10 persons asked information about 3D Tune-In.	
DA.038	Conference	The 12th International Conference on Intelligent Environments - IE'16 - 12-16th September 2016, London	12/9/2016-16/9-2016. London (UK)	Academia; researchers; scientific community.	http://www.intenv.org/	N/A	The workshop was attended by approximately 20 individuals, mainly academics (90%). The conference has a good impact on the academic community, and the extended abstract was included in the conference proceedings, maximising its potential impact	N/A

Section 5. Conclusions

This deliverable summarises the dissemination activities of the consortium up to month 18 (Oct, 2016). Table 17 presents a summary of performance indicators where estimations made at the beginning of the project for this period were compared with actual results.

Table 16: Key Performance Indicators M1-M18 vs Estimates

	Estimates (during the project lifecycle, 36 months)	Results (M1-M18)
Dissemination material	Brochure, posters, videos, website – Section 4.2. Project Materials	
Website	Efficiency (visitors, links, bounce rate, etc.) – Section 4.1. Website	
Social Media	Scale of success (fans/likes, shares, engagement rate) – Section 4.7. Social Media Activity	
Journal Articles	2	1
Conference publications	3	5
Scientific Workshops	3	3
EU and national project networked	3	5
M.Sc. Thesis	3	0
PhD Dissertation	1	1 in progress (Ms C. María Cuevas, UMA)

Figure 13 summarises the overall cumulative impact of partners’ dissemination activities and the impact measured on the website and social media channels.

Figure 13: Overall impact estimated

The industry players represent 26% of the estimated total audience; the general public represent 46%; and the academia/scientific community represent approximately 12%⁷.

The consortium has already exceeded many of its dissemination targets and expects to continue in this way over the next 18 months.

⁷ Source: Quarterly reports and Activity Reports provided by the partners.